
Critical Insights of Social Media: It's Impact on Society

Kamal Gautam¹, Gurudatt Kakkar², Kiran Soni³, Shalini Jain⁴

¹PhD Scholar, Carrier Point University Kota Rajasthan, India

²Carrier Point University Kota Rajasthan, India

³Associate Professor, Geetanjali Institute of Technical Studies, Udaipur, Rajasthan, India

³Assistant Professor, Geetanjali Institute of Technical Studies, Udaipur, Rajasthan, India

Abstract The invention of online social networks has been one of the most exciting events in this decade. Many online social networks such as Twitter, LinkedIn, and Facebook becoming popular day by day. In addition, multimedia networks such as Flickr also gaining increasing popularity in recent years. Now day's social networks are extremely rich in content, and they typically enclose a tremendous amount of matter and linkage data which can be leveraged for analysis. It has been noticed that in this present era, many people have become dependent on social networks, especially it's increasingly popular among youth with greater intensity which found good and bad impact on them and society, so even social networks are better, still its use should be limited or can say use as need.

Keywords Social Networks, effects of society in social network

Introduction

According to Bandura, (1986) [1], social networks have become very popular in recent years because of the increasing proliferation and affordability of internet enabled devices such as personal computers, mobile devices and other more recent hardware innovations such as internet tablets. This is evidenced by the burgeoning popularity of many online social networks such as Twitter, Facebook, and LinkedIn. Such social networks have to lead to a tremendous explosion of network-centric data in a wide variety of scenarios.

Social network scan be defined either in the context of systems such as Face book which are explicitly designed for social interactions, or in terms of other sites such as Flickr which are designed for a different service such as content sharing, but it isalso allowed at the extensive level of social interaction.

In general, a social network is defined as a network of interactions or relationships, where the nodes consist of actors, and the edges consist of the relationships or interactions between these actors. A generalization of this idea of social networks is that of information networks, in which the nodes could comprise either actors or entities, and the edges, denote the relationships between them [2]. Clearly, the concept of social networks is not restricted to the specific case of an internet-based social network such as Face book; the problem of social networking has been studied often in the field of sociology in terms of generic interactions between any groups of actors. Such interactions may be in any conventional or non-conventional form, whether they be face-to-face interactions, telecommunication interactions, email interactions or postal mail interactions.

Social Media Concept

Kubey (1998) [3] explored that now day's media becomes the part of education and even those parents who want their children smartly use the computer also agreed that, children will defiantly use the media for a better understanding of their studies. Parents believe that computer expertise can equal a leg up in the job market.

Joint (2011) [4] commented that “if the new technology is making us stupid”, then why people are not understanding its drawbacks. He has written in his journal “ANTAEUS” about the dependency of peoples on social media and asked the question as the title of his research: If Google makes you stupid, what should librarians do about it?

Social media being a concept is new that it also has not taken root in the dictionary of the code of ethics of Social Work Organizations. Yet, the point cannot be overstated that cutting edge Social Work Practice of the future will of necessity involve and include extensive use of social media and web-based activities [5].

Social Media Definitions

Ellison *et al* (2007) [6] define “Social media is using for social interaction with highly accessible and scalable communication technique. Social media is the use of web-based and mobile technologies to turn communication into interactive dialogue.”

Social media is most transparent, engaging and interactive form of public relations. It combines the true grit of real-time content with the beauty of authentic peer-to-peer communication [7].

Social media consists of various user-driven (inbound marketing) channels (e.g., Facebook, Twitter, Blogs, YouTube). These channels represent a stark difference from the advertiser-driven (outbound marketing) push model. Clearly as the principal owner of the customer relationship in the firm, typically, the marketing department is responsible for managing these social media channels. Even though some may argue that the customer relationship is everyone’s responsibility in the firm, the overarching responsibility rests having the marketing department clearly as the champion for the customer [8].

Social media is digital content creating interaction between people [9].

Business peoples using social media as a tool of marketing. They are doing their conversation with the customer and introducing their products to them easily. But can’t force them to pass this marketing message to others, it depends on their choice only. It’s the new form of media that does not exist until it happens and that cannot buy by advertisers to carry their messages [11].

Social media is focused on leveraging online tools that promote sharing and conversations, which ultimately lead to the engagement with current and future customers and influencers in their target market. The vital key to social media working is having a content marketing strategy that involves the distribution of valuable, relevant and compelling content that promotes the behavior peoples are looking by which they ultimately drive their business. Most businesses start with the tools. Effective social media starts with a content strategy that helps to position business and brand as the expert in niche through provocative, informative and helpful content. Then, once that is accomplished, the social media tools are now available today that make the plan coming together [11].

Effect of Social Media in Society: The Good, the Bad and the Ugly

The Good

The best thing with social media is a communication. People are living in a time where the world is open for all. People can contact anyone around in this world, at any time, with just a few keystrokes. It is free, unlike calling across the ocean, and live. This can also share that the good movements of life, by which people enjoying after sharing it with other peoples in terms of audio, video, photos animations etc. It has been like being a part of person’s world, even though distance keeps apart [12].

We also have the communication between people and businesses. Since they have paved an improved way for interaction between the two, customers are now telling brands exactly what they want. Businesses can then use that information to tailor their products of more appeal. They used to spend a ton of cash for this kind of marketing data. Customers spend hours on phones and obtaining more frustration when they suffered a problem or complaint.

There is also causes and information. Social media has made it possible for like-minded individuals to discuss important topics, widen their personal knowledge and discover things they never knew before. For example, young people around the world are now more involved than ever before in their country’s politics. The very last presidential elections in the US are evidence of that. Social media has contributed to that increase in a big way.

Non-profits are seeing the benefits of using social media for their own awareness campaigns. Sites like Facebook, Twitter, YouTube and others are a cost effective means of spreading the word and getting support. Not to mention socially shared petitions from sites like Causes.org, reaching hundreds of thousands of people.

The Bad

However, not all consequences of this technology are good ones. Much like the way it really has allowed us to hide behind screens and limited our social interaction face to face. People get the feeling of being social without having to go out and socialize. In the same vein, it gives the feeling of being a friend (or having friends) without having to place in any actual work to build the relationship. Just think of how many people have on Facebook friends list. Just how many of them will see on a semi-regular basis? etc. Then it has the issue that how it has taken our lives. Some time its making irritation when being out in public and seeing people on their phones. Seeing them talking never bothered some as long as they simply weren't being obnoxious. Nor does sending off an immediate text bug; maybe they are meeting someone and telling them where they are, or something. It is the obvious Facebooking or tweeting or whatever else that keeps people's eyes glued to their phones. People should not check social media sites when they are doing some important work. Whether it is grocery shopping, getting dinner with friends or waiting in line, it is just so impolite. It may also show a serious problem with distraction in today's society.

We can't enjoy the world around us for the hour without retreating back into that safe little digital box. Productivity is pretty much-shot thanks to social media, as well. Admit it, people check their profiles during work, or find themselves wandering over to YouTube to compliment their favorite blog during work hours. This is a fun little game: anytime that get distracted by a social media site, make a little strike on a piece of paper. At the end of the day, count all the strikes and feel our heart drop within our stomach as we try to estimate how much time wasted it represents.

The Ugly

Some of what social media has performed isn't just 'bad'; it is flat out 'ugly' even. It has also observed that a number of relationships have been broken up over social networks. Now, don't misunderstand that certainly not saying that Facebook is responsible for this. It is just a tool that has seemed to make it easier to cheat, and also to do things that cross a boundary in our relationship. Like flirty post with that high school that sweetheart you haven't seen since graduation. Or much more blatant infidelities that will sure to be caught the first time and forget to log out of a given computer and share with a spouse.

Literature Review

Lim et al (2012) [13] highlighted how and why Korean students using Social Networking Sites, what are the advantages they found by using Social Networking Sites. The study starts with the explanation of how the number of international students getting admission in US universities has increased. It may also refer to psychological experiences of international students for instance disorientation, nostalgic depressive reactions, and feelings of isolation, alienation, and powerlessness. However, international students may have limited ways to cope with stress, which could lead to stress-related illnesses particularly anxiety or depression. Hence these limitations ensure it is hard for international students to acclimatize themselves new circumstances.

The research was conducted in overall the United States of America with Asian international students, all from Korea, who were not raised in a western culture. Respondents in this study used Social Networking Sites in various ways and the tools played a necessary role in their adaptation to a higher life in the United States. Findings of a study clearly shown that the respondents benefitted because of the use of social networking sites and also that the interactions helped to decrease their anxiety within the new culture by providing all of them with a means of connecting with their parents and friends in Korea. Towards the end, it also stressed on the need for more research to recognize the potential of Social Networking Sites in contributing to the affective and cognitive adaptation for international students including the connection between Internet use and academic achievement.

In a study entitled “Social capital as Face book; Differentiating uses and users” Burke *et al* (2011) [14] discussed extensively regarding the perspective to look at the uses of Social Networking Sites. It says though usage of Social Networking Sites will often be treated as a monolithic activity, in which all time is equally social and also its impact the same for all users. The study primarily examines how toFace book affects social capital depending upon: types of site activities, contrasting one-on-one communication, broadcasts to wider audiences, and passive consumption of social news, and individual differences among users, including social communication skill and self- esteem.

In this particular study (2011) a survey was conducted using 415 Facebook users, which revealed that receiving messages from friends is associated with improvement in bridging social capital. The major aim of the study would be to observe how different uses of a large Social Networking Site influence different types of user’s social capital. Social capital will be the actual or potential resources which are linked to a durable network of more or less institutionalized relationships of mutual acquaintance or recognition. The study states that college students are motivated by social information-seeking, using Social Networking Sites to learn about people they have met offline, and expressive information sharking, feeling greater to bridge social capital.

His-Peng Lu (2011) [15] applied network externalities and motivation theory to comprehend the usage of Social Networking Sites among college students. After conducting an empirical research involving 402 samples, using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) Approach, His and Lu (2011) [15] realized that “Enjoyment” was the most influential factor for the increasing usage of Social Networking Sites among college students.

Folorunso (2010) [16] conducted a survey among students of the University of Agriculture, Abeokuta in Nigeria and tested the attributes of Diffusion of Innovations (DOI) theory towards usage pattern of Social Networking Sites. Demographic data considering the study revealed that majority of users were college students. The five constructs *i.e.* Relative Advantage, Complexity, Compatibility, Observability, and Reliability were used to test the impact on the attitude and trust regarding Social Networking Sites and to determine how attitude would impact on the intention to use it. The study revealed the constructs: relative advantage, complexity, and observability of Social Networking Sites do not positively have an influence on attitude towards using the technology while the compatibility and trial ability of Social Networking Sites do positively affect the attitude towards using the technology. The study (2010) concluded that the attitude of university students towards Social Networking Sites does positively affect the intention to use the technology.

As So-Youn *et al* (2009) [17] rightly pointed out that today the college students using numerous Social Networking Sites, to stay connected with their friends, discover new “friends” and also to share users – created contents, for instance, photos, videos, blogs etc. in order to explore factors affecting college students’ motive for using Social Networking Sites.

Steinfeld *et al* (2008) [17] studied on Social Networking Sites provides tough provoking insights. According to this study, 85 % concerning the respondents use one or more social networking sites. The extent of the usage of Social Networking Sites has increased dramatically in the past two years and the usage of Social Networking Sites as well differs considerably by age.

The majority of the respondents aging 18 and 19 years old use Social Networking Sites (95%), yet only 37% aging 30 years and above utilizes these networking sites. The majority involving 18 and 19 years old have greater than 200 friends while those aged 30 and above have more or less 25 or lesser friends on those sites. Consequently Face book are most commonly used Social Networking Site, with MySpace clearly as the second choice. Finally, it was also found that about half of such users utilize just one Social Networking Site, having only one profile, and participate in one to five groups within Social Networking Sites. Profiles of Social Networking Sites are fairly stable, with most respondents changing them monthly or less often. The majority of the users of Social Networking Sites spend 5 hours or less on a weekly basis. Younger respondents report spending more time than older respondents, additionally, it may also emphasize that almost all students (87%) put access restrictions for their own profiles. Younger respondents and females are most likely to achieve this.

Coyle and Vaughn (2008) [19] examined the literature on Social Networking Sites and conducted a survey on how college students are engaged in social networking. They found that the main purpose of using Social Networking Sites is to keep in touch with friends. They also indicate that these are used for merely trivial

communication with friends. These sites are a really new form of communication that really evolving over time with the help of technology.

Impact of Social Media on Society

It is clear from the literature that social media has an enormous impact on society. Many of the social media sites are the most popular on the web. Some social media sites transformed the way where people communicate and socialize on the web. Social networking sites render the opportunity for people to reconnect with their old friends, colleagues, and mates. It also helps people to make new friends, share content, pictures, audios, videos amongst them. Social media also changes the life style of a society.

Analysis & Interpretations

Figure 1: Usage of social media in the society

Social media sites 2014-2016 % of online use the following social media websites by year.

According to the survey conducted by the Pew Research Centre, in September 2016, total 67% online adults using two or more social media sites. More than half adults of age 65 and above use 72% of Face book which represents 29% of all seniors? Half of the internet-using young adults' ages 18-29 use 55% Instagram and half of the Instagram users (49%) use the site daily. The share of internet users with college education using LinkedIn reached 52%. And Twitter users 47% of online women now use the platform, compared with 16% of online men.

Positive Effects of Social Media on Society

- Social Media help to meet people they may not be having met outside of the social media forums.
- Additionally, it will help to share ideas beyond the geographical boundaries.
- It provides an open opportunity for all writers and bloggers to connect along with their clients.
- Another positive effect of social networking sites it unites people on a huge platform for the achievement of specific goals. This brings positive change within the society.
- Social media provides awareness among society like campaigns, advertisement articles, promotions which intensify the society to become up to date having the current information.

Negative Effects of Social Media on Society

- One of the negative effects of social media makes people get addicted them self. People spend lots of time on social networking sites which can divert the concentration and focus on the particular task.
- Social media can easily affect kids; the reason is sometimes people shares photos, videos on media that contain violence and negative things which can affect the behaviour of kids or teenagers.
- It also abuses the society by invading people's privacy.
- Social lies like family ones also weaken as people spend more time connecting with new people.

- Some people use their images or videos in social sites which some time used for the wrong purpose and negative intention by other people.

Conclusion

Finally, it concludes that the effects of social media have been somewhat balanced, to be honest. There are many good things about it, and many bad things. In the end, it can say if people keep their life cantered in reality and use social networking as a small part of it, their life becomes happier.

References

- [1]. Bandura, A. (1986). Social foundations of thought and action: A social cognitive theory. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice-Hall.
- [2]. Arseneault, L., Walsh, E., Trzesniewski, K., Newcombe, R., Caspi, A., & Moffitt, T. E. (2006). Bullying/victimization uniquely contributes to adjustment problems in young children: A nationally representative cohort study. *Pediatrics*, 118,130–138.
- [3]. Kubey, R. (1998). Obstacles to the development of media education in the United States. *Journal of Communication*, 48(1), 58-69.
- [4]. Joint, I., Doney, S. C., & Karl, D. M. (2011). Will ocean acidification affect marine microbes? *The ISME Journal*, 5(1), 1-7.
- [5]. Egan, K. G., & Moreno, M. A. (2011). Alcohol references on undergraduate males' Face book profiles. *American Journal of Men's Health*. doi: 10.1177/1557988310394341
- [6]. Ellison, N. B., Steinfield, C., & Lampe, C. (2007). The benefits of Face book "friends:" Social capital and college students' use of online social network sites. *Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication*, 12, 1143–1168.
- [7]. Olsen, Rasmus Friis, and Lisa M. Ellram. "Buyer-supplier relationships: alternative research approaches." *European Journal of Purchasing & Supply Management* 3, no. 4 (1997): 221-231.
- [8]. Burgess, Cheryl M., and Rafaela M. Quiroga. "Assessment of the safety and efficacy of poly-L-lactic acid for the treatment of HIV-associated facial lip atrophy." *Journal of the American Academy of Dermatology* 52.2 (2005): 233-239.
- [9]. Chen, Andrew, Sam Decker, and Maksim Borisovich Smolev. "Method and system for promoting user generation of content." U.S. Patent 8,214,261, issued July 3, 2012.
- [10]. Eisenberg, D., Downs, M. F., Golberstein, E., & Zivin, K. (2009). Stigma and help seeking for mental health among college students. *Medical Care Research and Review*, 66(5), 522–541. doi: 10.1177/1077558709335173
- [11]. Pulizzi, Joe. "The rise of storytelling as the new marketing." *Publishing research Quarterly* 28, no. 2 (2012): 116-123.
- [12]. Dunton, G. F., Liao, Y., Intille, S. S., Spruijt-Metz, D., & Pentz, M. (2010). Investigating children's physical activity and sedentary behavior using ecological momentary assessment with mobile phones. *Obesity*. doi: 10.1038/oby.2010.302
- [13]. Lim, Keol, and Ellen B. Meier. "International students' use of social network services in the new culture: A case study with Korean youths in the United States." *Asia Pacific Education Review* 13.1 (2012): 113-120.
- [14]. Burke, Moira, Robert Kraut, and Cameron Marlow. "Social capital on Facebook: Differentiating uses and users." *Proceedings of the SIGCHI conference on Human factors in computing systems*. ACM, 2011.
- [15]. Lu, His-Peng, et al. "Exploring the Stickiness of Social Networking Sites from the Perspective of Uses and Gratification Theory." *Business and Information* 3 (2010): 386-95.
- [16]. Folorunso, Olusegun, et al. "Diffusion of innovation in social networking sites among university students." *International journal of computer science and security* 4.3 (2010): 361-372.
- [17]. Jung, So-Youn, Wonshik Han, Jong Won Lee, Eunyoung Ko, Eunkyung Kim, Jong-Han Yu, Hyeong-Gon Moon et al. "Ki-67 expression gives additional prognostic information on St. Gallen 2007 and

Adjuvant! Online risk categories in early breast cancer." *Annals of Surgical Oncology* 16, no. 5 (2009): 1112-1121.

- [18]. Steinfield, Charles, Nicole B. Ellison, and Cliff Lampe. "Social capital, self-esteem, and use of online social network sites: A longitudinal analysis." *Journal of Applied Developmental Psychology* 29.6 (2008): 434-445.
- [19]. Coyle, Cheryl L., and Heather Vaughn. "Social Networking: Communication revolution or evolution?." *Bell Labs Technical Journal* 13.2 (2008): 13-17.

